

Using Ultra-High Speed Imaging to Identify the Material Properties of Composites at High Strain Rates

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PhotoDyn Project: www.photodyn.org

Introduction: Composites

- Transverse/shear properties driven by polymer matrix => Strain rate dependence

Background: Split Hopkinson Bar

- Assumption: neglect inertial effects => equilibrium
 - What about small strains to failure?

Background: Hopkinson Bar

- Limitations for testing composites off-axis with SHPB:
 - Low wave speeds + small strain to failure => inertial effects
- Strain rates limited to less than 1000 s^{-1}
 - Gilat et al. (2002), Comp Sci Tech 45° and 90°: dispersion at 400 s^{-1}

Gilat et al. (2002), Comp Sci Tech

Background: Image-Based Inertial Impact Test

- Standard SHPB neglects inertial effects

$F_1 + F_2 = \int \rho a dV$ \rightarrow $F_2 = \int \rho a dV$

- Can we measure inertial effects (' a ')?
 - Wave speed in 90° carbon fibre ≈ 2 km/s: >1 Million fps + full-field measurements
- Image-Based Inertial Impact (IBII) Test

Relating Acceleration to Stress

$$\sum \mathbf{F} = m\mathbf{a} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \int \sigma_{xx} dy = \rho \int a_x dS$$

Full-field measurements: integral \approx sum

$$\rho \int a_x dS \approx \rho S \frac{1}{N^S} \sum_{i=1}^{N^S} a_x^i, \quad N^S \text{ data points}$$

Average Over Height Average Over Surface

$$\overline{\sigma_{xx}}^y = \rho x_0 \overline{a_x}^S$$

Stress-Gauge Equation

L. Fletcher, F. Pierron, J. Dynamic Behavior Mater. 4 (2018) 481–504.

Raw Images to Material Response

Raw images

Grid Method:
1 measurement
per 5x5 px

Displacement field

Acceleration field

Strain field(s)

Stress-strain curve

$$\overline{\sigma_{xx}}^y = \rho x_0 \overline{a_x}^y$$

$$\overline{\epsilon_{xx}}^y$$

$$\overline{\epsilon_{xx}}^y$$

Off-Axis Stress-Gauge

Transverse (22)

$$\int \sigma_{22} dl = \rho \int a_2 dS$$

$$\overline{\sigma_{22}}^l = \rho \frac{S}{l} \overline{a_2}^s$$

Shear (12)

$$\int \sigma_{12} dl = \rho \int a_1 dS$$

$$\overline{\sigma_{12}}^l = \rho \frac{S}{l} \overline{a_1}^s$$

Average Over Angle Slice

Average Over Surface

Stiffness Identification: E_{22} , G_{12}

$$\overline{\sigma_{22}}^l \text{ vs } \overline{\varepsilon_{22}}^l \Rightarrow E_{22}$$

$$\overline{\sigma_{12}}^l \text{ vs } \overline{\gamma_{12}}^l \Rightarrow G_{12}$$

Test Design Process

1. Numerical Test Design

Select test parameters

2. Image Deformation

Select processing parameters

3. Experiments

Specimen Configuration: Off-Axis

- Composite: Gurit SE70 (Carbon/Epoxy) UD, $[45]_{15}$
- Full-Field Measurement: Grid, 0.9mm, 5px/period

Impact Rig and Imaging Setup

Gas Gun Impact Rig
Projectile Speed: 30-35ms⁻¹

Shimadzu HPV-X
(400x250px, 2Mfps)

Contact
Trigger

Waveguide

Specimen

Flash

Kinematic Fields: 45° Off-Axis

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Stress-Strain Curves: Off-Axis (22)

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1) $\overline{\sigma_{22}}^l = \rho \frac{S}{l} \overline{a_2}^S$ 2) $\overline{\sigma_{22}}^l$ vs $\overline{\varepsilon_{22}}^l \Rightarrow E_{22}$

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1) $\overline{\sigma}_{12}^l = \rho \frac{s}{l} \overline{a}_1^s$ 2) $\overline{\sigma}_{12}^l$ vs $\overline{\gamma}_{12}^l \Rightarrow G_{12}$

Stiffness Identification: Off-Axis (12)

$G_{12}(\text{Avg}) = 3.4 \text{ GPa}$

Future Work

- Strength Identification
 - Off axis linear stress gauge
 - Full stress tensor from acceleration: Image Based Stress Reconstruction (IBSR) - Dr Rian Seghir
- Full stiffness tensor in one test?

Summary

- Experimental validation of the IBI test for off-axis stiffness identification

- Future Work

- Off-axis strength identification
- Full stiffness tensor in one test?

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